

The Compound verbs in Greek and Latin Languages

An applied study on Genesis

This research examines the Structure and Semantics of the compound verbs in both Greek and Latin Languages, applied upon Genesis. It aims to trace the impact of hidden meanings of the examined text. It contains an introduction, two chapters, a conclusion, Arabic and English abstracts, and a list of sources and references.

The introduction mentions the aims of choosing this topic, the reason of selecting both the Septuagint, and the Vulgate, the real meaning of the compound verbs in the three languages dealt with: Greek, Latin and Arabic. It also shows the method dealt with in this research, the reference, and the lexica, and some various Arabic translations of the Bible.

The first chapter examines the structure and semantics of the compound verbs of both Greek and Latin Languages in the twenty- three significances relating to the creation and the power of God in Genesis, with the help of some linguistical and rhetorical devices such as alliteration, homoioteleuton, anaphora, climax, paronomasia, chiasmus, rhetorical question and hendiadyoin.

The second chapter investigates also the structure and semantics of the compound verbs of both Greek and Latin Languages in the twenty- three significances in Genesis relating to man's behaviours and activities with the help of the above mentioned linguistical and rhetorical figures.

This contrastive study has concluded that the knowledge of the compound verbs of both Greek and Latin Languages, with the interplay of the above mentioned linguistical and rhetorical figures help us in interpreting and revealing numerous and various hidden meanings in Genesis.